

**USAGE OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES VIS-A-VIS DEPRESSION AMONG
PG STUDENTS OF CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF PUNJAB**

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ABSTRACT

Social networking sites (SNSs) are Web-based platforms on which individuals connect with other users to generate and maintain social connections. Considerable disagreement exists as to associations that SNS use may have with depression. The present study was conducted to explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among PG students of Central University of Punjab. The total number of 200 students were selected by using stratified random sampling technique for the collection of data. The study found that maximum number of PG Students of Central University of Punjab comes under moderate level of usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression. The findings reveals that there is no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. Moreover, there is no influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. The study also reveals that there is significant impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among PG students of Humanities. It was also found that there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among PG students of Science stream students of CUPB and there is no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams.

Keywords: *Social Networking Sites, Depression, CUPB*

INTRODUCTION

Internet is one of the communications means in the modern era that has been used by humans. This means has increased the speed and accuracy of works in a better way and has expanded communications, in such a manner that the Earth has become a global village. Internet has the

ability to transfer millions of messages, messages that influence the values, attitudes and cultural identity of its users at the micro level and the socio-cultural system at macro level. This is in line with these changes that symbolic realities in Internet environment have provided the necessary ground for the formation of social media. Such a space known as a monolithic virtual reality, have features such as being beyond time and space, lack of restrictions on civil law-based states nations, concurrent availability, bring online and having cultural-religious-philosophical-economic spaces and freedom from new physical and sexual identities. In general, social networks refer to a group of people who communicate with one another in groups and share things such as their information, needs and thoughts, in other words, social media are sites that provide facilities for users to communicate within the framework of a network of personal and group relationships using a search engine and adding some features such as chatting, electronic messaging, sending image and sound and so on.

Social Networking Sites

Social networking sites are a new generation of web facilities that are in the center of Internet users' attention today. These kinds of sites work on the basis of the formation of online communities, and each one brings together the groups of Internet users with common interests or characteristics. These networks have become in fact a new kind of social media that have provided a new way of communicating and sharing information on the Internet. Hundreds of millions of Internet users are the members of hundreds of different social networks and spend a part of their daily online activities on these sites. Networks such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, YouTube, My Space, Orkut, and Flickr are among those virtual social networking sites that have grown rapidly in a short period of time and are becoming more and more popular among people day by day. Since communication is the main reason for users to use social networks and since users can communicate with a lot of people in a short period of time, it has led to the excessive use of these Social Networking Sites by users, especially youngsters and the youth. It also causes people to get more interested in communication in cyberspace rather than the communication in the real world, and this might threaten their psychological health. Disorders such as Internet addiction, anxiety, depression, identity disorder, reduction of feelings are among common disorders which get aroused due to the excessive use of social networking sites.

Social networks (SNS) are web platforms where people join with other users to generate and maintain social connections. There is a strong disagreement about the associations that the use of SNS can have with depression and anxiety. On the one hand, SNS can protect against mental illnesses, as they support and allow interaction and social connection. On the other hand, there are many opportunities for bad communication and badly managed expectations, and maladaptive trends can be exaggerated, leaving people to experience a greater sense of isolation. In general, the environment of SNS can be as difficult as face-to-face interactions. As SNS membership continues to increase, it is increasingly important to address the possible advantages and disadvantages that the use of SNS can have on mental health.

Depression

Depression is a disorder of mood, is a characterized by dejection, negative self-attitudes, indecisiveness, loss of motivation, disturbed sleep and sometimes by suicidal-preoccupation. In the early part of the twentieth century, a number of psychoanalysts sought to explain depression in the light of the prominent analytic theories of the time, as seen in the work of Karl Abraham, Sigmund Freud, Sandor Rado and somewhat later, Melanie Klein.

More recently, the study of depression has encompassed many diverse fields of scientific inquiry. Psychology and psychiatry are those fields that typically come to mind, but a wide ranging review of the fields that have examined depression include: biochemistry, genetics, social work, nursing, counseling, business, general medicine, biology, zoology, sociology, education, physiology, endocrinology and other disciplines. It is estimated that by the year 2020 if current trends for demographic and epidemiological transition continue, the burden of depression will increase to 5.7% of the total burden of disease and it would be the second leading cause of disability-adjustment life years (DALYs).

Signs and Symptoms

Depression typically affects multiple areas of individual functioning including emotional, motivational, behavioral, cognitive and somatic symptoms.

Most people who are depressed feel sad, loss of emotional expression, anxious or empty mood, they tend to lose their sense of humor. Many depressed people seem to lose their feelings of affections for friends and relatives.

Depressed people usually loss of interest in activities that were once initiative or enjoyable, including sex. Almost all report a lack of drive, initiative and spontaneity.

Depressed people spend more time alone and may stay in bed for long periods. Depressed people may also move slowly with seeming reluctance and lack of energy.

Depressed people hold decidedly negative views of themselves. They consider themselves inadequate, undesirable, inferior, perhaps evils. Depressed people usually blame themselves for nearly every negative event, even things that have nothing to do with them, and they rarely credit themselves for positive achievement. Their guilt and self-criticism may seem harsh to everyone else, but they see it as perfectly appropriate. Another cognitive symptom of depression is a negative view of the future. The feeling of hopelessness, helplessness, pessimism, guilt, worthlessness and social withdrawal also makes depressed people especially vulnerable to suicidal thinking.

Depression is often accompanied by such physical ailments as headaches, indigestion, constipation, unpleasant sensations in the chest and generalized pain. Infact, many depressions are initially misdiagnosed as medical problems. Depressed people loss of appetite with weight loss or overeating with weight gain and sleep disturbance with insomnia, early-morning awakening or oversleeping. Depressed people usually get less sleep overall than others and awaken more frequently during the night. At the other end of the spectrum, however are the approximately 9% of depressed people who sleep excessively. Depression differs from other behavior disorders of childhood and adolescence in its co morbidity with suicidal risk.

Rationale of the Study

Social networking sites (SNS) are online services that emphasize the creation of a connection between people to enable them to share their interests. These network sites allow people to share their information in a group. Therefore, the main purpose of the social networking sites is to allow people to share their real-life interests, activities and experiences. To some extent, Social

Networking Sites help common masses to share their feelings but many a time become a reason of arising Depression. Vitak (2008) reported in a study that there are several reasons why people use a social networking site. One of the reasons is that they meet strangers and become friends. Through social networking sites, users can keep their interpersonal relationship with their friends and users can send private messages, can use chat rooms and other methods of communication. Lack et. al. (2009) reported that most of the students who use social networking sites, can easily access other user profiles by using their account information. It further suggests that formal education should be presided over by students regarding the use of these sites. Bicen and Cavus (2010) reported in their study that the use and exchange of knowledge on the internet is an integral or internal part of the life of university students. The findings of the study also show that Live Spaces and Facebook are the sites commonly used by students.

Miller et. al. (2010) conducted a survey among students on the use of social networking sites and the capability of published content. The answers indicate that students regularly publish inappropriate content for all types of audiences, especially for potential employers. Das and Sahoo(2010) reported in their study that people use SNS for many purposes mainly because SNS offers the opportunity to express their points of view and provide independence and connect a person with millions of people in the world.Morallo (2013) conducted a study on effects of social networking sites and found that the use of SNS did not have a significant relationship with the academic performance of students. The rating improvement is based on other factors within the teaching-learning process and therefore cannot be attributed to the use of SNS alone.

Banquilet. al. (2009) reported in a study that "Social networking sites negatively impacting academic performance" and also indicated that friendship networks often require access to information and knowledge directly and indirectly and the effect of friendship on the academic performance of the students was confirmed. Fadardi (2009) conducted a comparative study of depression and found that both groups, the number of children and the years of education predicted depression levels. However, abused wives obtained higher scores in terms of depression, anxiety and stress than unused abusers.Panticet. al. (2011) conducted a study on social networks and depression and found that online social networks are linked to depression. Further research is needed to determine the possible causal nature of this relationship.

On the basis of reviews researcher find that Social Networking Sites are Web-based platforms on which individuals connect with other users to generate and maintain social connections. Some reviews are showing that users use Social Networking Sites for enjoyment. But some reviews show that use of SNSs may lead to stress, depression and anxiety. On one hand, SNSs may protect from mental illness, as they support and enable social interaction and allow users to reflect aspects of their identity and express emotion that may be relevant to their life experience. On the other hand, there are many opportunities for miscommunications and mismanaged expectations and maladaptive tendencies can be exaggerated, leaving individuals feeling a greater sense of isolation. Central University of Punjab (CUPB) is a university where students from all over the country come to make their future. Almost all the students of Central University of Punjab are using Social Networking Sites despite ban by the authorities. Still students use Social Networking Sites by using proxies showing the addiction of students towards Social Media. Hence my research work got an opportunity to explore the negative effect of Social Networking Sites like Anxiety, Stress and Depression on students of Central University Of Punjab. So the main focus of the research will be how the usage of Social Networking Sites leads to depression among the PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To examine the level of Depression among PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To explore the influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- To study the impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab
- To study the impact of usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab
- To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites of male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

- To compare the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.
- To compare the level of Depression among PG students of Science and Humanities stream of Central University of Punjab
- To compare the level of Depression among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Hypotheses of the Study

- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will come under higher level of usage of Social Networking Sites
- Majority of PG Students of Central University of Punjab will depict low level of Depression.
- There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among Male PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- There will be no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among Female PG Students of Central University of Punjab
- Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Depression among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab
- Usage of Social Networking Sites will put no significant impact on Depression among PG Students of Science stream of Central University of Punjab
- There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.
- There will be no significant difference in the usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab.

Delimitations of the Study

- The study was delimited to four Humanities and four Science Departments of Central University of Punjab.
- The Sample size was delimited to 200 students of Humanities and Science Stream of Central University of Punjab.

- The Sample size was further delimited to 100 male and 100 female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Research Methodology

In the present study, influence of usage of social networking sites and Depression on PG students of the Central University of Punjab, Bathinda. A sample of 200 post graduate students was taken and then classified according to their flows. The sample was further divided into gender wise and stream wise. The researcher used the stratified random sampling technique for collection of data. Data were collected from the Central Punjab University, Bathinda. The investigator used Depression scale (2011) by Pallavi Bhatnagar, Megha Singh, Manoj Pandey, Sandhya and Amitabh. Self-made Questionnaire on checking Usage of Social Networking Sites was developed by the investigator. The investigator used Percentage analysis, t-test as well as Correlation statistical technique for testing the hypothesis

RESULT

- Table 1.1 shows the Level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 1.1 that out of 200 students, 18% of the PG students fall under higher level of Usage of Social Networking Sites, 68% fall in the moderate level and 14% fall in the Low level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. It was found that majority of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Usage of Social Networking Sites. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Table: 1.1 Level of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG Students of CUPB

Usage of SNS	N	High Level of Usage of SNS	Moderate Level of Usage of SNS	Low Level of Usage of SNS
	200	18%	68%	14%

- Table 1.2 shows the level of Depression among PG students of Central University of Punjab. From table 1.2, it was found that 15.5% fall under normal level of Depression, 15.5% fall under Mild level, 51.5% fall under moderate & 17.5% fall under severe level of Depression. Hence, it was found that maximum number of the PG students of Central University of Punjab have moderate level of Anxiety. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.2: Level of Depression among PG Students of CUPB

Level of Depression	N	Normal level of Depression	Mild level of Depression	Moderate level of Depression	Severe level of Depression
	200	15.5%	15.5%	51.5%	17.5%

- Table 1.3 show the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table Table 1.3 that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression of male students of Central University of Punjab is -0.0118 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that from the table 1.3 that the coefficient of correlation is negative, so it can be hypothesized as there is no significant influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among male PG students of Central University of Punjab. Here, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.3: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among male PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of Social Networking Sites	100	198	-0.0118	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Depression	100				

- Table 1.4 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among female PG students of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 1.4, the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression of female students of Central University of Punjab is -0.1319 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no influence of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.4: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among Female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of Social Networking Sites	100	198	-0.1319	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Depression	100				

- Table 1.5 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among PG students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed from table 1.5 that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression of PG students of Humanities stream of CUPB is 0.0303 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that the coefficient of correlation is positive, so it can be hypothesized as there is significant impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among PG students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab. Here, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.5: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among PG Students of Humanities Stream of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of Social Networking Sites	100	198	0.0303	< 0.05	Positive Correlation
Depression	100				

- Table 1.6 shows the coefficient of correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among PG students of Science Stream of Central University of Punjab. It was revealed that the r-value of Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression of PG students of Science stream of CUPB is -0.1153 which is less than table value of r with the df of 200 at 0.05 i.e. 198. Hence r-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence it can be interpreted that the coefficient of correlation is negative, so there is a no impact of Usage of Social Networking Sites on Depression among PG students of Science stream students of CUPB. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 1.6: Coefficient of Correlation between Usage of Social Networking Sites and Depression among PG Students of Science Stream of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	df	'r' value	Level of Significance	Remarks
Usage of Social Networking Sites	100	198	-0.1153	< 0.05	Negative Correlation
Depression	100				

- Table 1.7 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab. From the table, it was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of male and female are 86.88 and 86.78 respectively. The S.D. of male students is 7.67 and that of female students is 5.96. Also the calculated t-value is 0.10 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.7: Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among the male and female PG students of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance
Male	100	86.88	7.67	0.10	< 0.05
Female	100	86.78	5.96		

- Table 1,8 shows the Mean, S.D, t- value and level of significance of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab. From the table 3.21 it was revealed that the mean value of Usage of social networking sites of Humanities and Science stream students are 87.56 and 86.1 respectively. The S.D. of Humanities student is 6.484 and that of Science students is 7.156. Also the calculated t-value is 1.50 which is less than table value of t with the df 198 at 0.05 level i.e. 1.98. Hence, it is concluded that the t-value is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between usage of Social Networking Sites among science and Humanities PG students of Central University of Punjab.

Table 1.8: Comparison of usage of Social Networking Sites among PG students of Science and Humanities streams of Central University of Punjab

Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	df	't' value	Level of significance
Humanities	100	87.56	6.484	198	1.50	< 0.05
Science	100	86.1	7.156			

CONCLUSION

In view the results of the present study the investigator recommends that students should be monitored about the usage of Social Networking Sites. The Students should be educated on advantages and disadvantages of using Social Networking Sites. The use of Social Networking Sites by students should focus on the academic excellence of those sites instead of using them for negative purposes. The students should be educated about the negative effects of Depression and the various precautions to avoid them.

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